

Tool 13

Citizen science data charter

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 2 – develop). The template is developed by Scivil, the Flemish Knowledge centre for citizen science, and set up as a supplement to the ‘[Guide to Data Charter for Citizen Science](#)’. It aims to make initiators of citizen science projects think about the data aspects of their project in an accessible way. It can also be used as a preparatory step to create a Data Management Plan for your citizen science project.

Please download this template to your own folder and fill it in on your local computer. If you have any further questions about this template, please contact info@scivil.be.

I. Project information

A. General information

i. Project name:

ii. Project goal:

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iii. Main activities:

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B. Data and software information

i. What types of data will be collected?

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ii. What types of software or platforms will be used and/or created?

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iii. What types of outputs (reports, publications, ...) will be created?

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¹ Sterken M., Capiou R., Members of the Scivil data management working group. 2021. Data Charter for Citizen Science: A basic set of principles to support open and interoperable citizen-science data. Scivil, 2021

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iv. What existing (meta-)data standards will be followed? (cfr. [Data Guide](#) part IV and V)

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iv. Draw up a conceptual data model: (cfr. [Data Guide](#) part III.16)

2. Preparation of the Data Collection phase

A. Personal and sensitive data collection

i. Will personal² or sensitive data³ be collected? Do you really need this data for your project/research? (cfr. [Data Guide](#) part II)

Data type (cfr. I.B.i)	What kind of personal/sensitive information will be collected?	Why is the collection of this data necessary for the success of the project?	Are there alternatives that do not include personal or sensitive data?

Examples of things that are considered personal or sensitive data:

- ✓ Personal data:
 - Names
 - Identification numbers
 - Location data from GPS/mobile phone
 - Physical information
 - Physiological information
 - Genetic information
 - Mental information
 - Economic information
 - Cultural or social characteristics
- ✓ Confidential data:
 - Passwords
 - Data protected by Intellectual Property Rights
 - Financial information
- ✓ Biological data:
 - Endangered (plant or animal) species
- ✓ Personal and sensitive metadata

ii. What actions will you take to ensure privacy protection of the collected sensitive data? These may include actions for pseudonymization, anonymization⁴ or encryption of the data.

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B. Privacy declaration

Does your privacy declaration have the following characteristics:

- ✓ Is it written in a language understandable for the citizen scientists?
- ✓ Is it easy to find (e.g. on your website)?
- ✓ Is it concise and accessible to read?
- ✓ Is it in a visually attractive format?

² Personal data are any information about an identified or identifiable natural person.

³ More information on <https://www.openaire.eu/sensitive-data-guide>

⁴ See [Data Guide](#) page 32; and [Guidance on Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation](#)

- ✓ Is it complete and correct?

C. Intellectual property (cfr. Data Guide part II.9)

i. Do citizens contribute to the project in a way that is prone to intellectual property rights such as:

- ✓ By providing data:
 - Photos
 - Videos
 - Self-written observations or texts
- ✓ By analysing data or developing a tool or product
- ✓ By making use of existing platforms or tools with 3rd party copyrights

ii. Are there other intellectual property rights to consider related to outputs that the project will create or any other aspect of the project?

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iii. Do you have a Terms and Conditions⁵ statement for citizen participation that is:

- ✓ Understandable for the citizen scientists
- ✓ Easy to find (e.g. on your website)?
- ✓ Concise and accessible to read?
- ✓ In a visually attractive format?
- ✓ Complete and correct?

3. Digital outputs

For each output of the project:

- Output description:
- Type of output:
 - ✓ Dataset
 - ✓ Publication
 - ✓ Software
- Can this output be published in an open format?
 - ✓ Yes --> under which licence for open publication? (cfr. [Data Guide](#) part I.2-4)
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 - ✓ No --> is there any metadata/description of the output that can be published openly?
- Publication platform: (cfr. [Data Guide](#) part I.5)
 - Where will the output be published?
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 - Are there any licence obligations linked to the use of the platform?
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- Global Unique Identifier for the output: (cfr. [Data Guide](#) part IV.19)
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⁵ This is where you let the public know the terms, rules, and guidelines for interacting with your project or using its outputs. This statement includes the rules and restrictions for the use of the project outputs (data, tools, platforms, ...) and intellectual property arrangements.

Checklist for open publication of outputs:

The output does not contain any:

- ✓ Privacy-prone information
- ✓ Sensitive information
- ✓ Potential issues with intellectual property rights or copyright